

On 2-Arylimino-4-Keto-1,3-Benzoxazines

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A few 2-arylimino-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazines have been prepared by the interaction of phenyl salicylate and S-benzyl 1-arylisothiocarbamides. Similar products have been isolated from the reaction of phenyl salicylate and Sym-1,3-diarylguanidines also.

Titherley¹ prepared 2-phenyl-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazine by the interaction of phenyl salicylate and phenyl benzamidine. Afterwards Deck and Dains² carried out the reaction of phenyl salicylate with S-methyl 1-phenylisothiocarbamide by heating at 180° for several hours and reported the formation of a compound, m.p. 189°. They assigned the structure 2-phenylimino-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazine (III) for this compound, on the basis of its hydrolysis with boiling sulphuric acid (40%) into 2,4-diketo-1,3-benzoxazine (V), m.p. 224°. In the present studies, when the reaction of phenyl salicylate and S-benzyl 1-phenylisothiocarbamide was undertaken at comparatively lower reaction temperature (110°–115°), a compound m.p. 209° along with phenol and benzyl mercaptan has been isolated. This compound on hydrolysis with a boiling mixture of alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid afforded the product, m.p. 226°, as described by Deck and Dains. Therefore, a reinvestigation of the reaction described by Deck and Dains appeared worthwhile. On repeating the reaction of phenyl salicylate and S-methyl 1-phenylisothiocarbamide under Deck and Dains' conditions the compound 189° was never isolated, instead the same compound m.p. 209° was observed to be formed.

Interaction of phenyl salicylate (I) and S-benzyl 1-phenylisothiocarbamide (II) at 110°–115° afforded a product m.p. 209° along with benzylmercaptan and phenol. The benzylmercaptan and phenol were identified by converting the former into dibenzylsulphide and later into phenyl benzoate by the reaction of bromine and benzyl chloride in alkali respectively. The product with m.p. 209° was likely to have structures III or IV. But the structure IV was ruled out on the basis of the following facts: (i) It was soluble in dilute alcoholic alkali, (ii) It showed the characteristic C = O and C = N bands in the IR spectrum, (iii) On hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid it afforded a diketo compound m.p. 226° which was assigned the structure 2,4-diketo-1,3-benzoxazine (V). Therefore, the product with m.p. 209° was assigned the structure 2-phenylimino-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazine (III).

On extending the reaction of phenyl salicylate to S-benzyl 1-*p*-tolyl/*p*-Cl-phenyl isothiocarbamides under similar reaction conditions also afforded the related 2-*p*-tolyl/*p*-Cl-phenylimino-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazines (III) along with benzylmercaptan and phenol. In the case of the reaction of phenyl salicylate and S-benzyl 1-*p*-Cl-phenyl isothiocarbamide

one more alcohol insoluble product m.p. 258° was obtained. It was insoluble in alcoholic alkali and had the chemical composition of IIIc. Therefore, it was likely to have the structure IVc. The following is the likely mechanism of the reaction :

where R = (a) phenyl, (b) p-tolyl (c) p-Cl-phenyl

Products similar to III have been isolated by the interaction of phenyl salicylate and 1,3-diarylguanidines at 110°-115°. These were identified through undepressed m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra of the corresponding compounds obtained by the interaction of phenyl salicylate and S-benzyl 1-arylisothiocarbamides. In this reaction formation of phenol and arylamines have also been established by the usual methods.

where R = R' = (a) phenyl, (b) p-tolyl, (c) p-Cl-phenyl.

The 2-phenyl/p-tolylimino-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazines (III) and one of the isomers with m.p. 240° (where R = p-Cl-phenyl), on hydrolysis with alcoholic hydrochloric acid afforded the same 2,4-diketo-1,3-benzoxazine (V), m.p. 226°, confirmed on the basis of the absence of C = N, characteristic frequency in its IR spectrum. In this reaction the related arylamines were also isolated in form of their hydrochlorides.

Phenyl salicylate (11 g.) on reaction with 1,3-di-*p*-tolylguanidine (12 g.) afforded a compound m.p. 216° (6 g.). (Found : N, 10.52; C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂ requires : N, 11.11%). It was found to be identical with the compound IIIb in all respects.

Expt. No. 3. 2-p-chlorophenyl-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazine (IIIc)

Reaction of phenyl salicylate (8 g.) with S-benzyl 1-*p*-chlorophenylisothiocarbamide (10 g.) under the above reaction conditions afforded a compound, crystallised with ethanol m.p. 240° (6 g.) (IIIc). (Found : N, 10.02; C₁₄H₉N₂O₂Cl requires N, 10.28%). This on hydrolysis afforded a compound m.p. 226° identified as 2,4-diketo-1,3-benzoxazine (V). In this reaction one more compound with m.p. 258° was isolated. It was dark brown in colour, insoluble in boiling ethanol (Found : N, 10.07; C₁₄H₉N₂O₂Cl requires : N, 10.28%). It was insoluble in dil. alkali. Therefore, it was assigned the structure 2-imino-3-phenyl-4-keto-1,3-benzoxazine (IVc).

The compound with m.p. 240° IIIc was also obtained by the interaction of phenyl salicylate (11 g.) and 1,3-di-*p*-chlorophenyl guanidine (16 g.) under the above reaction conditions. (Found : N, 10.27; C₁₄H₉N₂O₂Cl requires : N, 10.28%). The compound with m.p. 258° was not obtained in this reaction.

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